

Children, Young People & Families
Data and Insight Pack

There are 67,070 Children and young people under 18 living in Doncaster

Census 2021

Population change (%) by age group in Doncaster, 2011 to 2021

**Doncaster has
36,904
households with
dependant children**

**Children In Need (CIN):
the total number of open CIN
cases is 2,061.**

**Doncaster has 332 children
with a Child Protection Plan,
558 children are in care and
there are 237 Care Leavers.**

- increase in people aged 65 years and over
- decrease in people aged 15 to 64 years
- decrease in children aged under 15 years.

11.5% (15,393) of households with dependant children and are headed by couples that are either married or in a civil partnership.

They are most commonly concentrated in the following areas:

- 16.7% in Bawtry, Austerfield and Hayfield
- 16.2% in Bessacarr and Lakeside
- 15.5% in Cantley, Auckley and Finningley
- 15.4% in Sprotbrough

6.1% (8,103) of households with dependant children are headed by co-habiting couples

They are most commonly concentrated in the following areas:

- 9.5% in New Rossington
- 7.3% in Mexborough West
- 7.3% in Moorends

7.9% (10,512) of household with dependant children are headed by lone parents

They are most commonly concentrated in the following areas:

- 12.6% in Bentley and Toll Bar
- 12% in Moorends
- 10% in Stainforth

In 2020, 49% of children living in lone parent families were in relative poverty after housing costs compared to 25% of children living in married or cohabiting families.

There are considerable inequalities in exposure to poverty

Proportion of different groups in poverty, before and after housing costs: UK, 2019/20

Deprivation

Doncaster ranks 41st in the ranking for deprivation

21.8% of Doncaster's population are under the age of 18

The highest concentration of under 16's in Doncaster live in Bentley & Toll Bar, Adwick le Street & Woodlands, Balby Carr, New Rossington and Stainforth

These areas are amongst the 20% most deprived areas in the country

Life Expectancy at Birth by Ward - Female

Ward	Female-Age
Roman Ridge	87.16
Edenthorpe and Kirk Sandall	84.57
Bessacarr	83.83
Tickhill and Wadworth	83.76
Finningley	83.69
Sprotbrough	83.25
Norton and Askern	82.81
Hatfield	81.78
Stainforth and Barnby Dun	81.66
Wheatley Hills and Intake	81.57
Edlington & Warmsworth	81.34
Bentley	80.25
Balby South	79.90
Town	79.72
Armthorpe	79.65
Mexborough	79.55
Rossington and Bawtry	79.53
Conisbrough	79.50
Hexthorpe and Balby North	79.41
Thorne and Moorends	78.88
Adwick and Carcroft	78.30

A difference of **8.9 years** in the Life Expectancy of the residents in the neighbouring Wards of Roman Ridge and Adwick and Carcroft.

Life Expectancy at Birth by Ward - Male

Ward	Male-Age
Sprotbrough	82.72
Tickhill and Wadworth	82.06
Finningley	81.24
Roman Ridge	80.11
Bessacarr	79.93
Edenthorpe and Kirk Sandall	79.10
Hatfield	78.85
Norton and Askern	78.51
Armthorpe	78.47
Rossington and Bawtry	77.72
Stainforth and Barnby Dun	77.71
Edlington & Warmsworth	77.33
Wheatley Hills and Intake	77.29
Conisbrough	76.25
Thorne and Moorends	75.93
Bentley	75.87
Hexthorpe and Balby North	75.65
Adwick & Carcroft	74.98
Balby South	74.93
Town	74.67
Mexborough	74.14

A difference of **8.5 years** in the Life Expectancy of male residents in the neighbouring Wards of Sprotbrough and Mexborough.

**Fairness & Wellbeing
Commission**

Ethnicity

Children and young people from minority ethnic groups account for 19.3% of all children living in the area, compared with 36.1% in the country as a whole.

The largest minority ethnic groups of children and young people in the area are White Eastern European, including Gypsy/Roma communities (7.9%).

Pupil Lifestyle Survey 2022....

- 91% of secondary pupils identify their ethnicity as White, a further 2% are Mixed race, 2% Asian, 1% Black and 1% Chinese. 2% preferred not to give an answer and 1% described themselves as 'other'.
- 80% of primary pupils identify their ethnicity as White, a further 3% are Mixed race, 3% Asian, 3% Black with 1% Chinese.
- Ethnic minority pupils are less likely to continue full-time education past year 11, with 45% saying they are planning to do so, compared to 53% overall.
- Whereas the level of bullying is consistent across both cohorts, ethnic minority pupils are less likely to think that their school takes bullying seriously (20% compared to 27% of pupils of white ethnicity and overall). Likewise, 25% of ethnic minority pupils said the bullying stopped after they told someone about it. The comparable figures for those of white ethnicity and pupils overall are higher (both 34%).

Ethnic diversity in Doncaster has increased; the 2021 Census shows that the Doncaster population was 86.6% White British compared with 96.5% in 2001.

The proportion of children and young people with English as an additional language:

- in primary schools is 13.2% (nationally 21.2%)
- in secondary schools is 10.4% (nationally 17.4%)

The most common languages spoken by Doncaster residents after English
(Census 2021)

Polish	2.18%
Romanian	1.82%
Kurdish	0.23%
Slovak	0.23%
Turkish	0.21%
Lithuanian	0.18%
Arabic	0.17%
Nepalese	0.17%
Urdu	0.16%
Russian	0.15%
Latvian	0.15%
Bulgarian	0.14%
Punjabi	0.14%

There are **2800** Households in Doncaster where no adults speak English but at least one person aged 3-15 does use English as their main language

Pupil Lifestyle Survey 2022....

15% of Secondary school pupils and 24% of Primary school pupils speak another language at home.

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Child Poverty

32.4% - 21,470 children in Doncaster were living in poverty 21/22

Child poverty disproportionately affects Black and minority ethnic children, with 46% now in poverty compared to 26% of white British children.

Single parents are also significantly affected.

Child poverty across English regions
2014/15 to 2020/21

Replay

THE POVERTY LINE
IS 60% OF MEDIAN
INCOME

The poverty rate for children in families with three or more children was 42% nationally, compared with 23% and 22% among children in families with one or two children, respectively.

The tables provided here use the DWP/HMRC local indicators combined with information about housing costs at the local level to estimate poverty rates after housing costs (AHC)

This shows many children are in households with incomes net of housing costs that are below 60% of the median. (March 2022)

10,192 – ½ of children living in poverty in Doncaster are from working households

Free School Meals

When you eat at home, which of the following apply? Tick all that apply

Pupil Lifestyle survey 2022	All Secondary Pupils	Pupils receiving FSM
Eat with my family/ people in my house	75%	67 %
Eat at the table	59%	47%
I decide how much I want to eat	53%	47%
I am given a choice of what to eat	51%	48%
Mealtimes are enjoyable	49%	38%
Eat while watching television	49%	50%

13,828 of Doncaster pupils were **eligible for free school meals** just 10,774 (80 per cent) were in receipt of free school meals.

The proportion of children entitled to free school meals:

- in primary schools is 30.1% (the national average is 25.5%)
- in secondary schools is 31.8% (the national average is 26.9%)

free school meal eligibility is limited to those whose household income is less than £7,400 a year

Pupil lifestyle survey 2022

- 32% of those on FSM don't normally have anything to eat or drink at breakfast (compared to 28% of all pupils) and a further 28% only have a drink.
- Of those that did not eat lunch 76% of pupils in receipt of FSM said they did not feel hungry (compared to 58% for all pupils) & 38% said they did not like the food options (compared to 31% of all pupils)
- 56% of respondents entitled to FSM eat fruit and veg every day compared to 65% of all pupils

10,512 Households in Doncaster were lone parent Households

*12% of all Doncaster family households
(Census 2021)*

Lone parents and their children have poor health and social outcomes, disproportionately experiencing:

- depression
- psychiatric disease
- attempted suicide
- alcohol and drugs-related disease
- poor educational outcomes
- school behaviour problems

Many of these adverse outcomes can be attributed to high rates of poverty among lone parents

Doncaster saw Yorkshire and The Humber's joint third-largest percentage-point rise in the proportion of lone-parent households (from 11.0% in 2011 to 12.0% in 2021).

Around 90% of lone parents were women.

The average age of a single parent is 39 years

Lone parents are less likely to be employed with around 50% of lone mothers of a child aged 0 to 4 employed, rising to 75% when children are aged 5 to 16.

In 2020, 49% of children living in lone parent families were in relative poverty after housing costs compared to 25% of children living in married or cohabiting families.

JRF Minimum Income Standards 2022 Research

For a Lone Parent with 2 children: Minimum Income Standard is £38,400 pa

To achieve this, parents would need to be amongst the top 20% of earners in Doncaster

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Young Carers

Doncaster Pupil Lifestyle survey 2022....

- **6% of secondary school pupils** surveyed in Doncaster admitted to being young carers and amongst those young carers **just 8% said the school is aware** that they are a carer.
- **8% of primary school pupils** surveyed said that they were young carers and amongst those young carers **just 18% said the school is aware** that they are a carer.

What impact does being a young carer have?

Caring for someone can be very isolating, worrying and stressful. For young carers, this can negatively impact their experience in education. [Over a quarter of young carers aged 11-15 regularly miss school.](#) This can have a lasting effect on their life chances.

One in three young carers said that their caring role makes them feel stressed. Research also shows that 23% of young carers in the UK said that their caring role had stopped them making friends.

Another common problem for young carers is actually recognising themselves as young carers. It's usually only when they reach secondary school that they realise that their home life is different from that of their friends.

What is a young carer?

A young carer is someone under the age of 18 who helps to care for a family member, relative or friend.

As many as 1 in 5 children and young people are young carers in the UK.

What do young carers do?

As a young carer you might support someone who has a disability, a long-term illness, or a problem with alcohol or drugs. Without this help, they would struggle or not be able to cope.

Nationally...

- It is estimated that there are **800,000** young carers
- **27%** Miss school regularly
- **39%** of young carers said that nobody in their school was even aware of their caring responsibilities
- **1 in 3** carers reported having a mental health issue

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Disability

Families with disabled children face two specific challenges in addition to those faced by all families, which taken together increase their risk of living in poverty:

1. Considerable additional and ongoing expenses – **the cost of care for their disabled child**
2. Barriers to entering and sustaining employment – **the income penalty**

Children living in a family where someone is disabled had a poverty rate of 36% after housing costs, compared with 25% for children living in families where no-one is disabled.

DWP figures show that there are almost three times as many families with disabled children in the lowest income quintile as in the top quintile

Childhood disability is frequently a 'trigger event' for poverty, as a result of additional costs, family break-up and unemployment that can follow the birth or diagnosis of a disabled child

Pupil Lifestyle Survey 2022...

13% of Secondary pupils and 12% Primary pupils have a long standing illness.

6% of secondary pupils and 7% of Primary pupils have a disability.

- Whereas 5% secondary pupils overall say they are unable to get a restful nights sleep, 19% of pupils with disabilities or long-standing illnesses say the same.
- Being bullied at school over the last 12 months is an issue for 35% of pupils with a disability/long standing illness (compared to 20% overall). 17% say they have been bullied online and 11% say they have been bullied in town (compared to 8% and 5% secondary overall).
- Whereas 41% of those being bullied overall would tell their parents/carer, 'only' 36% of pupils with a disability/long standing illness would do so. 33% of pupils with a disability/long-standing illness said the bullying stopped after telling someone, about the same as average.
- 38% of pupils with a disability and/or long standing illness say they have experienced inappropriate comments, behaviour or unwanted attention of a sexual nature at school, compared to 23% overall.
- 36% of pupils with a disability/long standing illness say they have experienced a controlling and/or violent relationship in comparison to pupils overall (26%).

Between 2017 and 2022 pupils with special educational needs in Doncaster increased by 18.4% from 6264 to **7418**.

forecasts estimate that children and young people with Special Educational Needs will continue to increase and by 2027 the numbers will be around 8500.

Across England: SEN is most prevalent among boys at age 9 (23% of all boys), and for girls at age 10 (13% of all girls)

Nationally...

- those identified with SEN are more likely to speak English at home,
- Of the pupils who are eligible for free school meals in England almost a third are identified as having SEND.
- SEN are most prevalent in travellers of Irish heritage and Gypsy/Roma pupils with 30% and 26% respectively.
- Seven out of ten excluded pupils in England have SEND.
- Families of children with SEND are more likely to be pushed into poverty (perhaps as a result of the costs and/or family stress associated with their child's SEND status).

Pupil Lifestyle Survey 2022...

- 10% of Secondary pupils have a special educational need, a further 9% were unsure whether or not they do
- Of those with special educational needs 21% said they do not receive any help and a further 14% are unsure.
- 38% of SEN pupils are worried about their mental health, compared to 28% overall.
- 25% of SEN pupils say they currently don't feel happy with their life, compared to 15% overall.

Pupils attending academy schools are less likely to be identified as having SEND

Children from the most disadvantaged local authorities are less likely to be identified with SEND than children of similar backgrounds who live in more affluent areas. Families in poorer areas appear to have more limited support for their children and are likely to be subject to higher thresholds for accessing support.

Conversely, at a lower, neighbourhood level, children in the most disadvantaged neighbourhoods had substantially higher odds of being identified with SEND. However, significantly, within these poorer neighbourhoods, the most affluent children are most likely to be identified with SEND, indicating that better-off families are relatively more successful at securing support for their children.

90.85% of Doncaster residents aged over 16 described their sexuality as heterosexual in the 2021, compared to **77% of pupils** questioned in the 2022 Pupil Lifestyle survey

- More than half of younger LGBT+ people experience homophobic, biphobic or transphobic bullying in Britain's schools.
- Verbal, physical, and sexual abuse is more commonly reported in transgender youth compared to cisgendered youth.
- Nearly half of pupils who experience bullying have symptoms of depression.

Pupil Lifestyle Survey 2022....

49% of pupils were girls and 46% boys, 4% described themselves differently, 2% preferred not to answer.

77% of pupils identify as Heterosexual, 8% are Bisexual, 1% identify as gay and 3% identify as a lesbian. 5% identify as 'something else' and 6% prefer not to say.

- Less than the secondary average, 24% of LGBT+ pupils say they are unable to get a restful night's sleep at home (5% on average).
- LGBT+ pupils are less likely to participate with friends after school (34%) and in out of school clubs (14%) compared to the pupil average (52% and 27% respectively).
- LGBT+ pupils are less likely to say they enjoy physical activities, with 53% saying they enjoy it a lot/quite a lot, compared to 68% overall. Of those that don't enjoy physical activity, for 64% of LGBT+ pupils it is because they feel shy about their body (compared to 40% of pupils overall that say the same).
- Whereas 79% of pupils unconditionally say they get love and support from people at home if they are upset or worked about something, the figure decreases to 54% for LGBT+ pupils.
- 41% of LGBT+ pupils say they have been bullied at school within the last 12 months, compared to 20% overall. Additionally, they are also more likely to be bullied online (18% compared to 8% overall), near the home (12% compared to 5% overall) and at home (8% compared to 3% overall).
- 54% of LGBT+ pupils feel they are bullied because of their sexuality, compared to 23% of pupils overall.
- Whereas 'only' 15% of pupils overall say they are not/not at all happy with their life at the moment, the figure more than doubles for LGBT+ pupils (31%).
- LGBT+ pupils are more likely to say they have experienced loneliness in the past year (51% say always or a lot of the time) compared to 27% overall.
- A higher proportion of LGBT+ pupils have experienced violence (10% compared to 6% overall) and shouting and arguing (33% compared to 17% overall) at home.
- A higher than average proportion of LGBT+ pupils worry about the way they look and their mental health, more than any other cohort.
- Whereas overall 16% of pupils display an explicitly harmful or potentially dangerous behaviour (e.g. drinking alcohol, smoking and or self-harming) when worried about things, the figure increases for LGBT+ pupils to 33%.

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Mental health & Wellbeing

Almost a third of all children worry about their family having enough money to live comfortably. This goes up to nearly half in children from low-income backgrounds.

- More than half of 16–25-year-olds have seen their GP about their mental health
- One in six children aged 5-16 are likely to have a mental health problem. This figure has gone up by 50% in the last three years.
- Between 2021 and 2022 alone, the proportion of older young people aged 17-19 in England with a probable mental health disorder jumped from one in six to one in four.
- Children with a probable mental disorder are more likely to live in a home experiencing financial difficulty than those without.

Adverse Childhood Experiences

- One-third of mental health problems in adulthood are directly connected to an adverse childhood experience
- Adults who experienced four or more adversities in their childhood are four times more likely to have low levels of mental wellbeing and life satisfaction

Pupil Lifestyle Survey 2022...

Secondary School Pupils :

- 59% of pupils are 'happy' or 'very happy' with their life at the moment, which is 3% higher than last year. Young carers and LGBT+ pupils are more likely than other groups to say they are 'not/not at all happy' (29% and 31% respectively).
- In the last year, 71% of pupils say they have felt lonely at least sometimes.
- 17% of pupils have experienced being frightened by shouting/arguing, additionally 6% have experienced direct violence in the previous month.
 - Groups reporting much higher than average incidence of shouting and arguing are LGBT+ (33%), SEN (25%) and those with a disability (23%).
 - SEN (12%), LGBT+ and those with English as a 2nd language (both 10%) are the most likely to have experienced physical violence also.
- When faced with a problem that worries them or makes them feel stressed, just under half of pupils choose to keep busy by themselves (48%) and 37% will rest or sleep more. 16% say they would adopt one or more harmful or potentially addictive behaviours to alleviate the worries, such as :
 - cutting or hurting themselves (9%),
 - drinking alcohol (8%)
 - or smoking (5%),

Primary School Pupils:

- 70% of Primary pupils are 'happy' or 'very happy' with their life at the moment. The notable lower than average exceptions are Young carers, (56%), SEN pupils (64%), FSM and those with a disability (both 66%).
- 87% of primary pupils say they worry about something. The greatest worry is exams and tests. FSM pupils and young carers worry the most about family problems (24%).

57% of parents and 64% of grandparents think childhoods are worse today than previous generations.

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Childhood Obesity

A five year old from a low income background is twice as likely to be obese than a child from the most affluent background this becomes three times more likely at age 11 years.

27%
of 5 years olds are **overweight** or **obese**
4% worse than national average

38%
of 11 years olds are **overweight** or **obese**
3% worse than national average

Rates of severe obesity among children were around four times higher in the most deprived areas.

England value
Rate per 100,000 population
96.1

Only 22% of children aged between 5 and 15 met the physical activity guidelines of being at least moderately active for at least 60 minutes every day (23% of boys, 20% of girls).

children are able to recognise and crave brands at just 18 months old
(Obesity Health Alliance, 2017).

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Children's Oral Health

32.7% of 5 year olds in Doncaster have visually obvious dental decay,

with each child having around 4 teeth affected.

23.7% England
27% Y&H
(Fingertips 2021/22)

In 2019 Doncaster made headlines for the highest amount of 6-10 year olds having tooth extractions due to dental decay in the country.

Almost 9 out of 10 hospital tooth extractions among children aged 0 to 5 are due to preventable tooth decay

Figure 3.13 Slope index of inequality in prevalence of dental caries in 5 year old children in England, 2019

Children living in the most deprived areas of the country were almost 3 times as likely to have experience of dental decay (35.1%) as those living in the least deprived areas (13.5%)

the likelihood of having dental caries was significantly higher only for those children with overweight and very overweight. (PHE)

Pupil lifestyle Survey 2022...

- Just 38% of primary pupils have seen a dentist within the last year
- Fewer FSM & SEN pupils (both 34%) have seen a dentist in the last year
- Good oral hygiene is apparent amongst 94% of pupils who clean their teeth at least once a day. SEN pupils appear to show less attention, with only 88% saying they clean their teeth daily.

Maternal BMI status is shown to relate to health inequalities, particularly for women who live in the areas of the most deprivation who are almost two and a half times more likely to be obese at the start of pregnancy than women who live in areas of least deprivation.

Black women are almost four times more likely to die from childbirth than white women.
Women in the most deprived areas 2.5 times more likely to die than those in the least deprived areas.

Maternal obesity can result in negative outcomes for both women and fetuses. The maternal risks during pregnancy include gestational diabetes and preeclampsia. The fetus is at risk for stillbirth and congenital anomalies. Obesity in pregnancy can also affect health later in life for both mother and child. For women, these risks include heart disease and hypertension. Children have a risk of future obesity and heart disease. Women and their offspring are at increased risk for diabetes.

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Education

Department for Education figures show there were a total of **5,849** permanent or temporary **exclusions** across schools in **Doncaster** in the 2020-21 academic year – **this year Doncaster had the highest fixed period exclusion rate in the country**

31.6% of **secondary school students** in Doncaster are persistently absent from school (10% + absenteeism)

Exclusions - Autumn: Fixed Period Exclusion Rate | Percentile Rank Trend

IMD 2019 Score - This measures the lack of attainment and skills in the local population. Doncaster is **3rd most deprived** out of 151 Upper-tier local authorities for Education, Skills and Training

Pupil Lifestyle Survey 2022...

Secondary School Pupils:

- 72% of all pupils spend more than 3 hours a day looking at screens and 94% overall spend at least an hour.
- Whilst 55% of pupils don't think that screen time has any negative affects on them, 30% think screen time/time online affects their sleep.
- Almost all pupils have their own mobile phone at home and over half have access to their own laptop/computer, smart TV and games console. FSM pupils are below average on every question when it comes to device ownership.
- 99% of all pupils have an account or profile on social media.
- Overall, 59% of pupils say they have chatted online with people they haven't met in real life and a fifth (24%) have met someone in real life whom they first met online. Overall, pupils are meeting people 'in real life after chatting online' which are of the same age (76%).
- 46% have seen adult content and over half of all pupils have lied about their age to look at a website or play a game. English 2nd language pupils (58%), Year 10s (57%) and LGBT+ pupils (57%) are the cohorts most likely to have seen adult-only pictures online.
- 37% of pupils have received a sexting image. 7% of pupils have sent undressed/sexual images of themselves and a further 5% have had someone they know send or post images of them online. 24% have received images from someone they didn't know.

Primary School Pupils :

- 80% say they spend more than 1 hour a day looking at the screen.
- 96% of pupils have a social media account.
- 75% of pupils say their parents/carers know their passwords for online sites/apps and 56% of parents/carers will talk to their children about what they can do online.
- 38% chat online with people they don't know.
- A third of pupils have lied about their age to look at a website/play a game, as well as seeing images online that have upset them.

Pupil Lifestyle survey 2022

Proportion of Secondary school children in Doncaster who have seen knives used as threat (Pupil Lifestyle Survey 2022)

The current rate of First Time Entrants to the youth Justice system is 177 young people aged 10-17 per 100,000, equating to 51 young people. This represents Doncaster's worst performance against this measure for the past three years.

Pupil lifestyle survey 2022...

How do you rate the following in the area where you live?

- 72% feel safe/very safe when they're at school, 80% feel safe/very safe when they're out during the day
- 77% do so when going to and from school.
- 34% of pupils feel safe/very safe when going out after dark in the area they live
- Just 27% feel safe/very safe in Doncaster town centre.

A national survey found that:

- 14% of teenage children had been a victim of violence in the last 12 months
- 39% of teens had been a victim or witness of violence in the last 12 months
- 55% of teens said they'd seen real life acts of violence on social media in the last 12 months.

- Children who start to drink by age 13 are more likely to go on to have worse grades, to skip school and even to be excluded from school
- More than four out of ten (43%) young people who drink alcohol report they are drinking to cope in some way. This includes reasons such as believing it can 'cheer themselves up' or help them to 'forget about problems'.
- Among 10–17 year-olds who have ever had an alcoholic drink, 12% experienced serious harm (like trouble with the police, being a victim of crime, being taken to hospital or getting into a fight) because of their drinking.
- In England alone, more than 10,000 under-18s were admitted to hospital because of alcohol in the two years starting April 2017
- Compared to non-drinkers, underage drinkers are more likely to smoke tobacco, use cannabis or use other hard drugs.

Pupil Lifestyle Survey 2022....

Have you had a drink containing alcohol in the last 7 days, that was more than just a sip?

23% of secondary pupils have consumed alcohol within the last 7 days. The proportion increases above average for year 10s (33%), SEN (33%) and young carers (29%).

- On average, of the 23% who say they have had an alcoholic drink in the past 7 days, pre-mixed drinks such as WKD and VK are the most popular. Spirits have become more popular with 50% of alcohol drinking pupils consuming it in the last 7 days.
- For those pupils consuming alcohol, the home is the most likely place they will drink (64%), followed by 'a friend or relation's home' (27%). For the pupils consuming alcohol, the alcohol was most commonly provided by parents/carers (49%) followed by adult friends/family over 18 years old (24%).

7% of Year 6 pupils overall say they have had a drink containing alcohol that was more than just a sip.

Evidence shows that if people don't start using tobacco by age 26, they probably never will however in 2020 15.7% of 16–24 year olds smoke.

Most adult smokers have had their first cigarette or were already addicted to nicotine by the age of 18 and 90% of lifetime smoking is initiated between the ages of 10 and 20 years in the UK

The latest data from the ASH-Youth 2022 survey of 11 to 18 year olds in England show that:

- current smoking prevalence (including occasional and regular smoking) is 6% in 2022, compared with 4.1% in 2021 and 6.7% in 2020
- current vaping prevalence (including occasional and regular vaping) is 8.6% in 2022, compared with 4% in 2021 and 4.8% in 2020
- use of disposable vaping products has increased substantially, with 52.8% of current vapers using them in 2022, compared with 7.8% in 2021 and 5.3% in 2020

Nationally; 10.4% of 11-15 year olds have tried vaping, compared to 29.1% of 16-17 year olds. Among 18 year olds 40.8% report having tried vaping

Pupil Lifestyle Survey 2022...

Which statement best describes you about smoking?

83% of secondary pupils have never smoked at all. Year 10s are more likely than year 8s to have tried smoking. Young carers and SEN pupils are more likely than other groups to have ever tried smoking.

- Most pupils (91%) have heard of 'e-cigarettes' with awareness slightly higher amongst Year 10s than Year 8s. Young carers (46%), FSM (42%), English 2nd language pupils (37%) are the groups most likely to have tried or use e-cigarettes.

- 39% of pupils are living in a household where someone smokes. 14% use rooms at home which are also smoked in with 13% sometimes travelling in a car in which someone is smoking. Both these figures are an increase on the previous two years.

2% of Year 6 pupils say they have tried smoking, with 8% that have tried or occasionally used e-cigarettes.

- 37% of pupils live in a household where someone smokes and 15% use rooms at home which are used for smoking. 15% sometimes travel in a car when someone is smoking. SEN pupils, FSM pupils and young carers are more likely to be living in a household where someone smokes.

Pupil lifestyle survey 2022...

Have you ever taken any drugs to get high?

6% of secondary pupils have taken drugs. The proportion is significantly higher amongst SEN (14%), Young Carers (15%) and Ethnic Minority Groups (18%)

- A fifth (20%) of pupils know someone who takes drugs. Year 10s are more likely to know someone who takes drugs than the Year 8s (29% and 11% respectively). Young carers, LGBTQ pupils and girls, are more likely to know someone taking drugs, than pupils from other groups
- 46% of pupils believe at least some of their peers have taken cannabis in the past 7 days. This increases to 64% amongst Year 10s (compared to only 28% of Year 8s) and 52% amongst girls (compared to 38% of Boys).
- 6% of pupils say they have taken drugs to get high, most of which are Year 10 pupils. 48% of pupils say they would know where to get information and support about alcohol or drugs. SEN pupils appear the most aware of all the cohorts.

<i>Pupil lifestyle survey 2022...</i>	Never taken	Taken more than a year ago	Taken within last 12 months	Taken during last month
Q: This question is about your experience of drugs. Look at the list of drugs below and tick one answer from each row.				
<i>Base</i>	47	47	47	47
Amphetamines (e.g. speed, sulp, whizz, uppers)	91%	0%	0%	9%
Cannabis (resin, leaf of oil, e.g. hash, pot, skunk, dope, weed)	19%	6%	15%	60%
Ecstasy (e.g. MDMA, E, Doves)	87%	2%	0%	11%
Cocaine (e.g. snow, Charlie, coke, nose)	79%	4%	4%	13%
Natural (e.g. magic mushrooms)	89%	2%	0%	9%
Synthetic (e.g. acid, LSD)	87%	0%	0%	13%
Ketamine (e.g. Special K, Vitamin K)	85%	2%	0%	13%
Poppers (e.g. Liquid Gold, Rush, TNT)	89%	0%	0%	11%
Solvents used as drugs (e.g. glue, gas refills, aerosols)	77%	0%	4%	19%
Novel psychoactive substances (NPS, previously known as legal highs e.g. spice)	87%	2%	0%	15%
Other drugs	79%	2%	4%	15%

